

Speed and Torque Control of a BLDC Motor with PID Controller

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Abstract— The simulation, model of four switch three phase Brushless DC motor drive based on the concept of Switching functions. To drive the system effectively a Direct Phase Current(DPC) control method is implemented but Torque ripple generated in the commutation interval is one of the main drawback of BLDC motor .This Paper presents an original study on generated torque ripples due to phase commutation in four switch three phase inverter (FSTPI).Then a novel current control technique is developed to minimize the commutation torque ripple for speed range. The developed design model can be implemented using the Matlab/Simulink software.

Keywords—FSTPI- Brushless DC motor, Direct phase current, E/V ratio, Duty cycle.

I. INTRODUCTION

Brushless DC(BLDC) motor with trapezoidal back-EMF have been with used to their efficiency, high power/torque density, low maintenance and easy control method[3]. This is widely used for various purposes in consumer products and industrial applications. The cost reduction of variable-speed drives is accomplished by the two approaches. One is the topological approach and the other is control approach [8]. In topology, minimum number of switches is used to compose the power conversion circuit [1]. However, these days, the BLDC motor is attracting much interest, due to its high efficiency, high power factor, high torque, simple control, and low maintenance with those advantages we have been investigating the possibility of the reduced converter for BLDC motor drives with advanced control techniques. As a result we found that one switch leg (two switches) in the conventional six-switch configuration instead of the six switches the four-switch, three phase inverter(FSTPI) employs only four switches, a pair of complementary switches generating of 120° as propose a the direct phase current control technique based on the concept of switching functions[2].

The developed DPC method generates robust speed and torque responses but due to this switching function we have

the torque ripple may exist in practice. Torque ripple generated in commutation period is the main drawback.

Torque ripple generated in commutation intervals in the BLDC motor which deteriorates the precision of BLDC motor especially in high speed region[1]. In this paper, a control method that is E/V ratio in the current control switching block in BLDC motor.

II. ANALYSIS OF FOUR-SWITCH THREE-PHASE BLDC MOTOR DRIVE

The analysis is based on the Fig. 1 showing the four-switch BLDC motor drive, equivalent circuit and the following assumptions:

- 1) Stator resistance of all the windings are equal , self And mutual inductances are constant.
- 2) The motor is not saturated.

Fig.1 – Four switch BLDC motor drive equivalent circuit
Under the above assumptions, a BLDC motor can be Represented as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{V}_1 \\ \dot{V}_2 \\ \dot{V}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \\ i_3 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} L_1 - M & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L_2 - M & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & L_3 - M \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \\ i_3 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where, V_x, e_x and i_x ($x=a,b,c$) represent the terminal voltage, trapezoidal back-EMF voltage and the current of